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DEVELOPMENT, PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF GLIPIZIDE SPHERICAL AGGLOMERATES BY DIRECT COMPRESSION METHOD.

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present research is to develop glipizide spherical agglomerates with improved solubility, flow and compression characteristics by novel crystallization technique. Glipizide was dissolved in 30ml dichloromethane (good solvent) and stirred. 100ml of water (poor solvent) was added and continued stirring. 5ml of chloroform (bridging liquid) was added and stirred at 1000rpm for 40 minutes to precipitate glipizide. Agglomeration process was optimized for parameters like speed and duration of agitation, volume of bridging liquid added. The precipitated particles were filtered and dried at 40°C. Spherical agglomerates were characterized by IR spectroscopy, X-ray diffractometry, DSC and SEM and its results revealed that there is no physical or chemical interaction existed in agglomerates. Spherical agglomerates exhibited decreased crystallinity and improved micromeritic properties (bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, angle of repose). The obtained agglomerates of glipizide were spherical and dissolution rates were faster and exhibited improved solubility, dissolution rate and micromeritic properties than pure drug. Direct compressible tablets of the glipizide agglomerates showed hardness, friability and weight variation appropriately with improved drug release. Among the different control release polymers Caesalpinia spinosa (natural mucoadhesive polymer) was showing highest drug release retarding capacity. F2 was showing the satisfactory results and having better sustainability. When we plot the release rate kinetics for best formulation f2 was following zero order because correlation coefficient value of zero order is more than first order value. F2 formulation diffusion exponent n value is $0.45 < n > 0.89$ so they are following Anomalous (Non-Fickian) diffusion. It indicates that the prepared spherical agglomerates gives good yield when compared to that of the pure drug.

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INTRODUCTION

Formulation and manufacture of solid oral dosage forms, and tablets especially, have undergone rapid change and development over the last several decades. Spherical crystallization techniques are the novel innovation in particle engineering in which crystallized drug particles are tailored to spherical agglomerates, which can be utilized for direct compression to save money and time for tableting. In direct tableting method, it is necessary to increase flowability and compressibility of the bulk powder in order to retain a steady supply of powder mixture to the tableting machine and sufficient mechanical strength of the compacted tablets. In addition to increasing efficiency of the manufacturing process it is also important to increase bioavailability of the drug by improving the solubility of the bulk drug powder. Spherical agglomeration is one of such techniques to improve the micromeritic properties and dissolution of the drug [1]. Spherical agglomeration is a process of formation of aggregates of crystals held together by liquid bridges. The agglomerates are formed by agitating the crystals in a liquid suspension in presence of binding agent [2]. It is the latest technique of enlarging smaller particles of solid into large size by inter-particle agglomeration [3, 4]. This technique can also be exploited to increase solubility, dissolution and hence bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs [5, 6]. Direct tableting is most desirable, easy and simplest technique of manufacturing tablet. Such manufacturing process of tablets involve simple mixing and compression of powder, which result in number of overall benefits including time, cost and energy savings. Direct compression of drug into tablet requires good micromeritic properties, such as good flowability, and good reproducible compressibility.

Glipizide is an oral rapid short acting anti diabetic drug from the sulfonyl urea class. It is classified as a second generation sulfonyl urea, which means it undergoes enterohepatic circulation. It is more potent and have shorter half lives than first generation sulfonyl ureas. The aim of the present study was to develop agglomerates of glipizide with improved flow characteristics and improved bioavailability when compared to that of a pure drug. Polymers like sodium alginate, ethyl cellulose, caesalpinia spinosa (natural polymer) were used with different viscosity grades and formulations were made using these polymers. Evaluations were performed for all the prepared batches for better results.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Glipizide drug was obtained as a gift sample from Dr. Reddys laboratories, Hyderabad. Ethyl cellulose and sodium alginate was obtained as a gift sample from Astra Zeneca Bangalore, India. All other chemicals used were of pharmacopeial grade. All solvents employed in this study were of analytical grade and used as it was received.

EXTRACTION OF NATURAL MUCOADHESIVE MATERIAL FROM CAESALPINEA SPINOSA:

1. Collection and authentication of plant:

The seeds of caesalpinia spinosa were collected from in and around areas of Nellore district. The plants were authenticated by Prof. K. Madhava Chetty, Department of Botany, SV University, Tirupathi, Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh and seeds specimen samples were kept in the laboratory for further use.

Caesalpinia spinosa, a small tree of family Leguminosae. Commonly known as Tara is a gum obtained from the endosperm of seed of Caesalpinia spinosa. Tara gum is an odorless, white powder; produced by separating and grinding the endosperm of the mature black colored seeds of Tara plant. The major component of the gum is a galactomannan polymer similar to the main components of guar and locust bean gums. In various pharmaceutical and food industries, Tara gum is used as a thickening agent and a stabilizer around the world. Further studies also gave an idea about its applications in various patents like; the use of tara gum as a controlled release formulations includes a gastro retentive controlled release tablets and emulsions for various drugs [7-9].

2. Extraction of natural mucoadhesive materials:

The collected seeds were washed thoroughly with water to remove the adhering materials. 500gm of dried seeds were soaked separately in distilled water (2500ml) for 24 hr and then boiled for one hour with continuous stirring at 2000rpm and then kept aside for the release of natural gum into water. The soaked seeds were taken and squeezed using several folds of muslin cloth to separate the marc from the filtrate. The marc was not discarded but it was used for multiple extractions. All the extractions were pooled and concentrated under vacuum at 60°C to half of the volume. Then to the filtrate equal quantity of acetone was added to precipitate the natural mucoadhesive material, which was then separated by filtration. The precipitated mucilage was dried at 60C in a hot air oven. The dried mucoadhesive agent was powdered, passes through the sieve no.100 and stored in an airtight container at room temperature for further use. This natural mucoadhesive material is used for different formulations.

PHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF SPHERICAL AGGLOMERATES

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) study [10-14]

A DSC study was carried out to detect possible polymorphic transition during the crystallization process. DSC measurements were performed with a thermal analyser.

FT-IR Spectroscopy [10-14]

The FT-IR spectral measurements were taken at ambient temperature using a Shimadzu, model 8033(USA). Samples were dispersed in KBr powder and the pellets were made by applying 5 ton pressure. FTIR spectra were obtained by powder diffuse reflectance on FTIR spectrophotometer.

X-RAY Analysis[10-14]

X-Ray powder diffraction patterns were obtained at room temperature using Bruker diffractometer, with Cu as anode material and graphite monochromator, operated at a voltage of 40mA, 45kV.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) [10-14]

SEM (Shimadzu-LV-5600, USA, with magnification of 250X) photographs were obtained to identify and confirm spherical nature and surface topography of the crystals.

PREPARATION OF GLIPIZIDE SPHERICAL AGGLOMERATES

Glipizide was dissolved in 30ml dichloromethane and stirred 100ml water was added and continued stirring. 5ml of chloroform was added and stirred at 1000rpm for 40min to precipitate glipizide. The precipitated recrystallized agglomerates were collected by vacuum filtration and dried in oven at 40°C for 6hr. The dried crystals were stored in desiccators at room temperature before use. The above process was repeated several times to obtain enough materials for characterization and to observe repeatability. Formulation codes were given for spherical agglomerates with polymers (ceasalpinea spinosa, ethyl cellulose and sodium alginate) from F1 to F9 and for pure drug with polymers from F10 to F18 respectively.

Drug content:

Drug content was determined by taking spherical agglomerates of glipizide equivalent to 100mg glipizide were triturated and dissolved in a solvent system containing dichloromethane: water: chloroform (30:100:5 v/v). Diluted samples were filtered through 0.45µ injection filter and drug content was determined spectrophotometrically at 276nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer(Lab india, UV 3000+)

Yield and Micromeritic properties

Yield of the prepared agglomerates were determined by weighing the agglomerates after drying. Bulk density (sisco), tapped density were determined by tap density tester and carr's index and hausners ratio were determined. The flow behaviour of raw crystals and spherical agglomerates was determined by angle of repose by using fixed funnel method.

PREPARATION OF GLIPIZIDE TABLETS

Glipizide agglomerates equivalent to 10mg of glipizide were manually mixed with directly compressible microcrystalline cellulose and the blend was finally mixed with magnesium stearate for 2 min. final blend (200mg per tablet) was compressed using rotary tablet machine with 6mm standard concave punch. The weight variation of the tablets was determined taking weight of 20tablets using electronic balance. Hardness, thickness, friability of tablets were studied by Monsanto Hardness tester, vernier calipers (Cd 6°Cs), Roche friabilator (ELECTRO LAB) respectively.

Evaluation of glipizide tablets *In Vitro* dissolution study [10-16]

The dissolution studies of raw crystals and spherical agglomerates of glipizide were performed by using USP 26 type II dissolution test apparatus (electro lab 08L) in 900ml of pH 7.5 phosphate buffer. Temperature was maintained at 37±2°C and 50rpm stirring was provided for every dissolution study. At predetermined time intervals, 5ml of samples were withdrawn and analysed spectrophotometrically. At each time of withdrawal, 5ml of fresh corresponding medium was replaced into the dissolution flask. After filtration through Whatman filter paper, concentration of glipizide was determined spectrophotometrically at 276nm. The cumulative amount of drug release versus time was calculated and plotted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FT-IR Spectra of glipizide

Glipizide pure drug & Glipizide spherical agglomerates

All the crystals have exhibited general characteristic peaks at 3030-3351cm⁻¹(3351 cm⁻¹ for NH-CO-NH stretching, 3030 cm⁻¹ for aromatic C-H stretching). Specific changes in IR spectra are not very clear, could be due to variations in the resonance structure, rotation of a part of a molecular or certain bonds as mentioned in Fig:1.

X-RAY Diffraction spectra of glipizide

All the samples showed similar peak positions in X-ray diffraction. The relative abundance of the planes exposed to the X-Ray source would have been altered, producing the variations in relative intensities of the peak or may be due to differences in crystal sizes as shown in Fig:2.

DSC Results

The DSC thermograms shows a sharp endothermic peak for all the glipizide crystals as shown in Fig:3. Melting points show slight variation as the nature of the crystals might have been affected by the solvent.

Scanning electron microscopy of glipizide

Crystals of pure sample are of smallest size (4-10 μ m) and have irregular shapes. Recrystallization product crystals have intermediate size (9-15 μ m), Fig: 4. The agglomerates were formed by coalescence of the microcrystalline precipitates, so the agglomerates had a rugged surface. Agglomerates obtained were spherical in shape with size 198 μ m- 670 μ m.

Dissolution profiles:

The dissolution profile of glipizide exhibited improved dissolution behavior for spherical agglomerates than pure sample. Spherical crystals exhibited decreased crystallinity and improved micromeritic properties. Amount of bridging liquid, speed of agitation and duration of agitation affects the mechanical and micromeritic properties of spherical crystals. DSC and XRD studies showed that there is no change in the crystal structure of glipizide during the crystallization process i.e. polymorphism is not present. DSC results further supported IR spectroscopy results, which indicated the absence of any interactions between drug and additives used in the preparation. Hence the spherical agglomeration technique can be used for formulation of tablets of glipizide by direct compression with directly compressible excipients. On the other hand, all prepared spherical agglomerates exhibited good compressibility which indicates good packability. The saturation solubility studies indicate that the pure drug having the least solubility while as the formulations have the higher solubility. Among the different control release polymers *Caesalpinia spinosa* was showing highest drug release retarding capacity. F2 was showing the satisfactory results and having better sustainability. When we plot the release rate kinetics for best formulation f2 was following zero order because correlation coefficient value of zero order is more than first order 2 value. F2 formulation diffusion exponent n value is $0.45 < n > 0.89$ so they are following Anomalous (Non-Fickian) diffusion.

Fig 1: FTIR Spectra of glipizide pure drug & glipizide spherical agglomerates.

Fig 2: X-Ray diffraction spectra of glipizide.

Fig 3: DSC Spectra of glipizide.

Fig 4: Scanning Electron Microscopy of glipizide.

Table 1: Composition of glipizide spherical agglomerates.

Ingredients(mg)	Spherical agglomerates of glipizide API									Glipizide API								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13	F14	F15	F16	F17	F18
Drug	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
mccph112	158	148	138	158	148	138	158	148	138	158	148	138	158	148	138	158	148	138
caesalpinia spinosa	30	40	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	30	40	50	-	-	-	-	-	-
sodium alginate	-	-	-	30	40	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	30	40	50	-	-	-
ethyl cellulose	-	-	-	-	-	-	30	40	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	30	40	50
mg stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

MICROMERITIC PROPERTIES

Table 2: PRECOMPRESSION PARAMETERS.

Formulation code	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Tapped density (g/cm ³)	Cars index	Hauers ratio	Angle of repose(θ)	Diameter
f1	52	59	11.86	1.13	32.81	7.94
f2	55	61	9.84	1.11	30.45	7.99
f3	49	57	14.04	1.16	33.64	8.02
f4	51	57	10.53	1.12	31.73	8.06
f5	55	62	11.29	1.13	32.67	8.04
f6	53	60	11.67	1.13	33.76	7.96
f7	57	67	14.93	1.18	35.42	8.01
f8	53	58	8.62	1.09	27.83	7.94
f9	51	59	13.56	1.16	36.79	7.97

f10	53	61	13.11	1.15	32.87	7.97
f11	57	65	12.31	1.14	34.73	8.02
f12	51	63	19.05	1.24	37.25	7.98
f13	53	62	14.52	1.17	34.26	7.99
f14	52	64	18.75	1.23	38.64	8.03
f15	56	64	12.50	1.14	33.16	7.95
f16	52	63	17.46	1.21	37.38	8.04
f17	55	63	12.70	1.15	33.62	8.02
f18	55	68	19.12	1.24	37.98	7.96

Table 3: POST-COMPRESSION PARAMETERS.

Formulation code	Weight variation(%)	Thickness(mm)	Hardness(Kg/cm ²)	Friability(%)	Drug content
f1	Pass	2.94	9.34	0.43	99.54
f2	Pass	3.12	9.83	0.21	99.62
f3	Pass	2.87	10.15	0.37	100.14
f4	Pass	2.85	11.12	0.15	100.57
f5	Pass	3.15	9.38	0.28	100.89
f6	Pass	3.22	9.72	0.36	99.37
f7	Pass	2.97	10.48	0.38	99.92
f8	Pass	3.18	10.39	0.23	100.53
f9	Pass	3.13	11.03	0.25	101.62
f10	Pass	3.12	9.93	0.47	100.12
f11	Pass	3.27	10.02	0.28	99.93
f12	Pass	2.97	10.37	0.38	100.36
f13	Pass	3.16	9.93	0.18	99.17
f14	Pass	2.99	10.75	0.48	100.32
f15	Pass	3.24	9.85	0.29	100.93
f16	Pass	3.19	10.51	0.32	99.27
f17	Pass	3.04	10.75	0.42	100.28
f18	Pass	2.92	9.93	0.26	99.29

DISSOLUTION PARAMETERS

Table 4: Drug release kinetic profile of glipizide tablets.

Formulation code	R ² Values				'n' Value
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	
F1	0.949	0.959	0.995	0.996	0.420
F2	0.990	0.984	0.991	0.994	0.574
F3	0.988	0.996	0.993	0.998	0.612
F4	0.808	0.996	0.933	0.964	0.295
F5	0.848	0.988	0.956	0.980	0.320
F6	0.890	0.982	0.976	0.986	0.359
F7	0.914	0.961	0.985	0.990	0.398
F8	0.940	0.983	0.994	0.995	0.410
F9	0.953	0.980	0.995	0.993	0.428
F10	0.930	0.984	0.990	0.998	0.369
F11	0.982	0.989	0.994	0.992	0.508
F12	0.980	0.991	0.996	0.996	0.511
F13	0.774	0.996	0.911	0.947	0.268
F14	0.815	0.977	0.937	0.975	0.282
F15	0.860	0.936	0.960	0.977	0.321
F16	0.887	0.977	0.974	0.989	0.354
F17	0.922	0.960	0.988	0.992	0.378
F18	0.943	0.950	0.992	0.992	0.396

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dissolution profile of glipizide exhibited improved dissolution behavior for spherical agglomerates than pure sample. Spherical crystals exhibited decreased crystallinity and improved micromeritic properties (Table: 2). Amount of bridging liquid, speed of agitation and duration of agitation affects the mechanical and micromeritic properties of spherical crystals. DSC (Fig: 3) and XRD (Fig: 2) studies showed that there is no change in the crystal structure of glipizide during the crystallization process i.e. polymorphism is not present. DSC results further supported IR spectroscopy (Fig:1) results, which indicated the absence of any interactions between drug and additives used in the preparation.

Hence the spherical agglomeration technique can be used for formulation of tablets of glipizide by direct compression with directly compressible excipients (Table: 1). On the other hand, all prepared spherical agglomerates exhibited good compressibility which indicates good packability. The saturation solubility studies indicate that the pure drug having the least solubility while as the formulations have the higher solubility. Among the different control release polymers *Caesalpinia spinosa* was showing highest drug release retarding capacity. F2 was showing the satisfactory results and having better sustainability. When we plot the release rate kinetics for best formulation f2 was following zero order because correlation coefficient value of zero order is more than first order value. F2 formulation diffusion exponent n value is $0.45 < n > 0.89$ so they are following Anomalous (Non-Fickian) diffusion (Table: 4). Higuchi plots F2 formulation is having good correlation values so the drug is releasing diffusion mechanism.

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DECLARATION/ CONFLICTS OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that there is no conflicts of interest to declare.

CONCLUSION

Glipizide spherical agglomerates were prepared which showed improved flowability, solubility, packability and compactability resulting in successful direct tableting without capping. The main factor in the improvement of the flowability and packability was a significant reduction in interparticle friction, due to spherical shape of the tabletted particles. Agglomerates were directly compressed into tablet with quick disintegration time and produced higher dissolution rate. It concludes that direct compression of spherical crystallization of glipizide with selective polymers is a satisfactory method to improve compressibility as well as dissolution of glipizide. Further research is to be done for invivo study to assess the bioavailability parameters of prepared glipizide agglomerates.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

FT-IR	- Fourier Transformer InfraRed Spectroscopy
DSC	- Differential Scanning Calorimetry
XRD	- X-Ray Diffraction
SA	- Spherical Agglomeration
KBr	- Potassium bromide
USP	- United States Pharmacopiea
Nm	- nanometer
API	- Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
Mg	- milligram
Mm	- millimeter

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